

CORTEX²

D6.1 – CORTEX² Impact Master Plan

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D6.1 - CORTEX² Impact Master Plan

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Abstract

The present document presents a detailed overview of CORTEX² communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy, vital elements of any successful Horizon Europe-funded project, while defining the goals, priorities and potential implementation mechanisms to achieve all desired outcomes. Furthermore, CORTEX² Impact Master Plan sets out the tools, materials, and channels to be exploited to effectively disseminate the project activities, achievements and tangible results to targeted audiences, becoming the cornerstone for the successful commercialization and market uptake of the project solutions

Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
CTA	Call to Action
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
EC	European Commission
EDIHS	European Digital Innovation Hubs
EIT	European Institute of Innovation & Technology
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
H2020	Horizon 2020
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Intellectual Property Rights
KEA	Key Exploitable Asset
OC	Open Call
RTO	Research and Technology Organisation
SC	Subcommittee
TC	Technical Committees
VR	Virtual Reality
WGs	Working group
XR	Extended Reality

The CORTEX² project

The COVID-19 pandemic pushed individuals and companies worldwide to work primarily from home or change their work model to stay in business. Today, all the signs are that remote work is here to stay. But not all organizations are ready to adapt to this new reality, where team collaboration is vital.

Existing services and applications aimed at facilitating remote team collaboration — from video conferencing systems to project management platforms — are not yet ready to efficiently and effectively support all types of activities. And extended reality (XR)-based tools, which can enhance remote collaboration and communication, present significant challenges for most businesses.

The mission of CORTEX² is to democratize access to the remote collaboration offered by next-generation XR experiences across a wide range of industries and SMEs.

To this aim, CORTEX² will provide the following:

- Full support for **augmented reality (AR) experiences** as an extension of video conferencing systems when using heterogeneous service end devices through a novel Mediation Gateway platform.
- Resource-efficient **teleconferencing tools** through innovative transmission methods and automatic summarization of shared long documents.
- Easy-to-use and powerful **extended reality (XR) experiences** with instant 3D reconstruction of environments and objects, and simplified use of natural gestures in collaborative meetings.
- Fusion of vision and audio for **multichannel semantic interpretation**, and enhanced tools such as **virtual conversational agents** and **automatic meeting summarization**.
- Full **integration of internet of things (IoT) devices into XR experiences** to optimize interaction with running systems and processes.
- **Optimal extension possibilities and broad adoption** by delivering the core system with **open APIs** and launching **open calls** to enable further technical extensions, more comprehensive use cases, and deeper evaluation and assessment.

Overall, **we will invest a total of 4 million Euros in two open calls**, which will be aimed at

1. recruiting tech start-ups/SMEs to co-develop CORTEX²
2. engaging new use cases from different domains to demonstrate CORTEX² replication through specific integration paths
3. assessing and validating the social impact associated with XR technology adoption in internal and external use cases

The CORTEX² consortium is formed by 10 organizations in 7 countries, which will work together for 36 months.

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1. Introduction

The current document outlines the initial CORTEX² Impact Master Plan. It includes the **overall project dissemination, communication and exploitation strategies**, and kick starts an extensive stakeholder engagement strategy, which will be the basis for community building and impact generation.

The plan is the result of a coordinated effort among partners, considering stakeholders' categories and needs as well as partners' communication channels and tools. In this sense, it is a supporting tool for each partner in maximizing the impact of their own dissemination actions while providing means to ensure high visibility of activities and outcomes of the project as a whole. This plan proposes a list of suitable communication & dissemination tools and activities for engaging the target groups in the project. To this end, a multi-step and multi-channel dissemination strategy is proposed in order to maximize the impact of the dissemination activities, adjusting the materials and tools to the specific needs, interests, and potential for involvement of the target audience.

The CORTEX² consortium considers this plan a living document, reflecting an open, ongoing dialogue with potential users and related networks during the project to be inclusive and ensure the best possible results.

2. Agile Stakeholder Management

2.1. Stakeholder Engagement Strategy

Identifying and engaging with the most relevant stakeholders is an activity often referred to as ‘community building’, and it is a key aspect of every Horizon Europe project, such as CORTEX² (as in the predecessor H2020). Indeed, the programme relies on communities, initiatives, and projects that will either use the outcomes or relate and possibly liaise with its activities along its course.

Creating and nurturing an ecosystem of key players around an initiative is always a crucial factor in the outcomes and success of its value stream. The stakeholder’s impact on a project depends on its potential power - the ability to influence the value proposition - and the interest in exercising that power. Assessing the stakeholder’s impact on CORTEX² will help to decide where to devote time and effort to achieve the greatest benefits.

When it comes to addressing fundamental challenges in Innovation, multiple initiatives often work in a standalone manner to address the same issue from various directions, incurring inefficiencies and being incapable of delivering their full potential. By adopting an open framework of collaboration with peers and groups that can benefit from and contribute to the project’s impact, CORTEX² will reach a deeper understanding of the requirements and benefits of aligning efforts with similar task forces. This is because it requires a responsive growth factor capable of prospecting and creating brand-new synergies over the project’s lifetime, facilitating a greater advantage and extending its range of action.

2.1.1. Engagement Framework

To maximise the effectiveness of the dissemination, communication & exploitation plans that will be introduced in this document, the consortium requires a mechanism for managing in a systematic manner the ever-changing list of organisations, initiatives, and players with a position to influence the value streams of the project.

For this reason, CORTEX² will implement the **Agile Marketing Lab Framework**[©], a methodology designed by AUSTRALO and based on an Agile Stakeholder Engagement framework, designed to continuously develop and strengthen relationships with a significant audience through the values of the **Agile Manifesto**¹:

The Agile Manifesto Principles		
Individuals and interactions	over	processes and tools
Results	over	comprehensive documentation

¹ <http://agilemanifesto.org/>

The Agile Manifesto Principles		
Collaboration	over	formality
Responding to change	over	following a plan

Table 1 Agile Manifesto Principles

- **Individuals and interactions over processes and tools:** Ecosystem building is a team-based approach to deliver value as a joint effort. Tools are an important part of projects, but the team needs to work together effectively through productive interactions with the stakeholders.
- **Results over comprehensive documentation:** It is much more valuable to interact with the stakeholders, obtain continuous feedback, and manage increments of the ecosystem’s snapshot rather than overspending resources on studying and reporting about their profiles and potential objectives.
- **Collaboration over formality:** This framework is designed to promote and facilitate cooperation in the programme. The team aims to engage and collaborate with stakeholders to inspect and adapt the vision so that the project will be as valuable as possible.
- **Responding to change over following a plan:** Rather than maintaining a fully defined and static vision of the stakeholders from the project, this methodology focuses on building up an ecosystem of interested parts throughout its lifetime.

The framework follows an iterative implementation structure based on **Sprints**, time-boxes of 6 months where the main goal is to continuously increase and reinforce the engagement of the stakeholders with the initiative. A new Sprint starts immediately after the conclusion of the previous. Its workflow includes the following phases:

Figure 1: Stakeholder Engagement Framework

- **Phase 1 – Analysis:** Building upon the objectives of **CORTEX²**, this phase will explore, map and assess Target Groups - and specific candidates - with different degrees of relevance for the scope and impact of the work plan. **CORTEX²** will build upon the sound experience and active involvement of the consortium members in initiatives and players that must be considered as a baseline for engagement, taking advantage of new leads generated by second-degree partnerships and new opportunities as an outcome of the Interaction phase, including emerging initiatives and Horizon Europe projects. The key result will be an initial version of the ‘Stakeholder Map’, a graphical instrument to 1) list key actors -and specific candidates within them; 2) thoughtfully organise and correlate these audiences; 3) define a common terminology to be used in all the project’s reference.
- **Phase 2 – Interaction:** The next stage will imply the interaction as such with the identified target groups, supporting the activities outlined in the Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation strategies. This is the phase where **CORTEX²** will collaborate with those initiatives deemed of special interest. Such interaction will include:

 - Lead generation –a one-to-many approach on prospective building awareness and lead generation over time, reaching out to a critical mass of players.
 - Prospecting –one-to-one actions focused on a specific set of prospects of the target audience. This type of interaction will include individual email exchanges, meetings, and follow-up actions.

Whenever relevant, the project will formally join specific Task Forces and Working Groups, contribute to scientific publications and participate in events. Feedback

extrapolated from previous Sprints will be used to enhance the efficiency and impact of these measures.

- Phase 3 – Learning:** The fundamental asset in an agile methodology is integrating lessons learnt during the execution, feeding the next iteration with insights to optimise the plan. Hence, from the actions performed during the interaction, the consortium will learn lessons and collect findings that will feed the next Sprint. This will also include insights obtained from consultations (e.g., in the form of quick questionnaires or interviews) and gathering valuable external remarks about the project and its operation. CORTEX² will adapt the channels and measures from ‘Interaction’ to new specific needs and opportunities.

2.1.2. Target Audience & Stakeholders

Promoting CORTEX² and encouraging stakeholders to engage with the initiative requires understanding who the ‘target audience’ is. Understanding these profiles and their influence in the value chain is essential to crafting the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plans.

Figure 2: CORTEX² Target Audience

Industrial Ecosystem

This category includes:

- Decision-makers and managers** from enterprises of the Industrial Ecosystem who design the digital transformation strategies in their organisations:
 - Industrial Managers

- Factory / Plant Managers
- Production Line Managers
- Digital / Innovation Managers
- R&D Departments / Units
- As well as **workers** implementing them.

The ambition of this group is to boost productivity, accomplish efficient resource management and improve safety conditions.

CORTEX² will engage with **members from relevant sectors directly involved in the validation process** to obtain feedback to support the implementation of the project and its use cases validation, get access to quality data and raise awareness of the benefits of immersive technology.

Digital Technology Providers

Such as **those who develop research outputs, innovation findings, business activities and standardisation efforts** around the eXtended collaborative technologies, such as:

- XR Platform/Service Developers,
- Component/Peripherals Manufacturers,
- Video Conference Platform Providers,
- AI Engineers/Data Scientists,
- Enterprise Solution Providers,
- Standardisation/Open Source TCs

Their objective is to investigate, advance and demonstrate the technical features offered by CORTEX².

The project will engage representatives in the 'Lab-To-Market' stage to support the Technology Transfer towards the 'Industrial Ecosystem', bridging the Open Innovation gap.

This category includes:

- **Research-oriented institutions:** technical universities, RTOs, spin-offs
- **Business-driven organisations:** from highly risk-taking startups to innovation units in large-scale industry

Which will:

- Contribute to the technical ambition of the project,
- Represent the main target audience for the open call campaigns.

Technical committees driving standardisation and open-source efforts are also considered.

Social Innovation Sector

The implementation of XR technology involves not only technical but also human and ethical factors, which are compulsory to facilitate a transformation compliant with the workforce's needs. **Social science innovators** need to be involved in order to:

- Identify the challenges,
- Strengthen the opportunities for user friendliness,
- Empower a smooth transition to the Future of Work, preventing workers from continuously adapting to ever-evolving technology.
- Foster a more attractive, safer and sustainable industry, pointing out opportunities for up/re-skilling.

CORTEX² is committed to the [New European Bauhaus](#), the interdisciplinary initiative situated at the crossroads between social inclusion, science and technology.

Partnerships and Networks

CORTEX² intends to leverage the knowledge and outreach capacity of initiatives advocating for the computing continuum and funding opportunities, using the consortium's participation in active ecosystems, to create synergies and reinforce awareness of the open calls and project outputs, using resources such as:

- **International open communities** built by consortium partners
- **Technical projects emerging from Horizon Europe's** mission in eXtended Reality technology and other related initiatives, such as:
 - [HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01-13: eXtended Reality Modelling \(RIA\)](#)
 - [SERMAS](#) - Socially-acceptable Extended Reality Models and Systems
 - [UTTER](#) - Unified Transcription and Translation for Extended Reality
 - [VOXReality](#) - Voice driven interaction in XR spaces
 - [HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01-14: eXtended Reality for All – Haptics \(RIA\)](#)
 - [ABILITY](#) - Haptic Tablet for the Accessibility of Digital Content to the Visually Impaired
 - [HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01-25: eXtended Collaborative Telepresence \(IA\)](#) (CORTEX² topic)
 - [SPIRIT](#) - Scalable Platform for Innovations on Real-time Immersive Telepresence
 - [HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01-06: Innovation for Media, including eXtended Reality \(IA\):](#)
 - [EMIL](#) - European Media and Immersion Lab
 - [MAX-R](#)- Mixed Augmented and eXtended Reality media pipeline
 - [TransMIXR](#) - Ignite the Immersive Media Sector by Enabling New Narrative Visions

- [XRECO](#) - XR mEdia eCOsystem
- [HORIZON-CL4-2022-HUMAN-01-14: eXtended Reality Technologies \(RIA\)](#):
 - [DIDYMOS-XR](#) - Digital DYnaMic and respOnsible twinS for XR
 - [SHARESPACE](#) - Embodied Social Experiences in Hybrid Shared Spaces
 - [SUN](#) - Social and hUman ceNtered XR
 - [THEIA-XR](#) - Making The Invisible Visible for Off-Highway Machinery by Conveying Extended Reality Technologies
- [HORIZON-CL4-2022-HUMAN-01-19: eXtended Reality Learning - Engage and Interact \(IA\)](#):
 - [MASTER](#) - Mixed reality ecosystem for teaching robotics in manufacturing
 - [XR2Learn](#) - Leveraging the European XR industry technologies to empower immersive learning and training
 - [XR4ED](#) - eXtended Reality for Education
- [HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01-28eXtended Reality Ethics, Interoperability and Impact \(CSA\)](#):
 - [XR4Human](#) - The Equitable, Inclusive, and Human-Centered XR Project
- Moreover, other future Horizon Europe-funded projects, operating and researching in the same domain as CORTEX², are also a key stakeholder group with which the project will seek to create active synergies.
- The same applies to those recently finished and present HORIZON 2020 or national projects, especially those participated by the partners, and which results are being used in CORTEX², such as [EYES OF THINGS](#), [MOVEON](#), [LARA](#), [LinTO](#), [Work@Home](#), [SUMM'RE](#), [LabForSims2](#), Autre or [SymbloTe](#).
- **European partnerships and associations** advocating for data and XR technology, such as:
 - [XR4EUROPE](#)
 - [Big Data Value Association](#)
 - [Gaia-X European Data Infrastructure](#)
 - [Women in Immersive Technologies](#)
- **Ecosystems concentrating large number of SMEs**, including:
 - [European Digital Innovation Hubs](#) (EDIHS)
 - [EU Innovation Council](#)
 - [EIT Digital](#)
 - Acceleration and incubation programmes
 - Regional clusters linked to the consortium, such as:
 - [Le Voice Lab](#)
 - [Pôle Mer Bretagne Atlantique](#)

- [La filière santé numérique](#)

Policy Makers

Members of a government department, legislature, or other organisations responsible for making new policies and promoting strategies for strengthening Europe's digital transformation, human capital and competitiveness.

Therefore, contributing to **policy task forces or working groups** (where and when relevant) shaping policies related to SSH and digital transformation, cannot be left outside the equation, as are a key part of CORTEX² engagement target. Specially the **European Commission**, with emphasis on the [EU Alliance for Industrial Data, Edge and Cloud](#).

The Society

The general public should not be overlooked. It is crucial to inform the public about the benefits of digital transformation, as well as encourage a common understanding and trust of the positive impact of human-machine interaction, that shifts the focus from technology-driven progress to a human-centric and sustainable approach.

2.2. [Stakeholders Map](#)

The figure below contains the first version of the CORTEX² Stakeholders Map, which graphically summarises all the target audiences at this stage. This diagram has been defined by taking into consideration the different target stakeholders' groups identified so far as the outcome of the ongoing Sprint of the Agile Stakeholder Framework.

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Figure 3: CORTEX² Stakeholders Map

3. Dissemination and Communication

Dissemination and Communication in Innovation Projects are key and necessary elements for achieving their desired impact. According to the European Commission:

“Dissemination means sharing research results with potential users - peers in the research field, industry, other commercial players and policymakers. By sharing your research results with the rest of the scientific community, you are contributing to the progress of science in general.”²

“Communication in Research and Innovation projects is a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures to communicate to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.”³

3.1. Dissemination Plan

To this end, **CORTEX² has developed a flexible and adjustable Dissemination Plan** that aims at building effective awareness of the project results, creating understanding and aiming for action among the key target audience identified. The execution of this strategy will facilitate the best use and uptake of the outcomes and research insights generated throughout the project’s lifetime, reinforcing each of the impacts in the work plan.

3.1.1. **The ‘3 phases’ approach**

Dissemination activities will be carried out in **three main phases**. Each of these has specific objectives and will therefore perform specific actions using appropriate channels. These phases will be presented and discussed during the first months of the project and will be refined accordingly to **match the priorities of CORTEX²**.

²https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/dissemination-of-results_en.htm

³https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/communication_en.htm

Figure 4: Dissemination Plan Phases

Phase I: Analysis (M01-M09). In this preliminary phase, the consortium will analyse the project's framework, with special attention to internal and external barriers and obstacles that could slow down the dissemination activities. It will also define the priorities and actions for the first half of the project.

Australo, the Dissemination and Communication Leader, coordinates the engagement activities to align the dissemination and communication activities with the needs of the stakeholders identified, creating general awareness about the project's objectives and expected results.

During this phase, the CORTEX² dissemination plan is prepared and delivered, along with the branding, website, social media and the first set of promotional material produced.

Phase II: Increase impact (M10-M18). The main objective of Phase II is to increase the awareness generated during Phase I, with a **special focus on the first Call of Proposals** of the project, as well as to expose the main CORTEX² achievements up to that point.

The Dissemination & Communication Leader will adapt the channels and measures identified in the proposal phase (and refined during Phase I) to the specific needs of Phase II, and it will work to properly find the right means to engage and collaborate with the target groups. This will help increase the potential impact of the project's results.

Participation in workshops, organisation of ad hoc events, as well as organisation of tutorials/webinars (if needed) will boost the dissemination process. Specific PR material will be also produced.

Phase III: Adoption (M19-M36). This phase will leverage the general awareness raised in Phase I and II, this time with a **special focus on the second Call of Proposals**, as well as attracting more potential target segments to the CORTEX² results, in order to increase impact **and sustainability of the project outcomes**.

First, the Dissemination, Communication Leader and Exploitation Leader will evaluate the outcomes of Phase I and II and, if needed, it will refine the priorities, channels and measures previously settled, also in concertation with the agile stakeholder management activities. Secondly, it will define the main activities that could increase the impact beyond the project's lifetime, such as continuing use of events, participation in workshops and conferences, and contributions to publications in targeted specific online media and printed trade and research journals.

3.1.2. Objectives

The main and key objectives of the dissemination strategy are as follows:

- To set up the information dissemination mechanisms and priorities of CORTEX².
- To establish, maintain and grow a community around CORTEX² in coordination with the stakeholder management framework.
- To create visibility and promote the work and results for target stakeholders by creating promotional material and information campaigns.
- To disseminate projects and outcomes to the widest possible community through various channels and instruments. External participation and knowledge sharing will be encouraged through networking activities and events aimed at increasing the impact potential and enriching the contribution to the project.
- To liaison with other EU, national and international initiatives to maximise the impact.

3.1.3. Measures

In order to execute the dissemination plan, the consortium identified a number of measures that need to be implemented throughout the project, enabling to reach the above-mentioned objectives in the most efficient and effective way.

In the following table, the **dissemination material** is outlined:

MATERIAL			
Measure	Description	Benefits	Stakeholders
Project Documentation	Material describing and reporting on technical outputs, APIs, architectures, models, recommendations, promotional activities and any kind of insights acquired by the consortium.	Publicly available information which can be disseminated and infused similar to CORTEX ² initiatives and to the community as a whole.	Industrial Ecosystem, Tech Providers, Social Innovators, Policymakers
Peer-reviewed Publications	Over 10 peer-reviewed scientific items in top refereed scientific	Ensure the project's technical achievements and experimental findings will be	Tech Providers, Social Innovators

MATERIAL			
Measure	Description	Benefits	Stakeholders
	journals and 10 peer-reviewed papers in relevant conferences.	known and exploited by the larger research community and related scientific domains.	
Non-scientific Publications	Release and contribute to over 50 publications; blog posts, articles, position papers and any other non-scientific publication oriented to end-users and the public society.	Widespread awareness, uptake and validation among a broad audience.	Industrial Ecosystem, Partnerships, Policymakers, Society
Coding Guidelines	Guidelines to ease external development efforts, including 'code of conduct', 'Development environment', 'security guidelines', 'coding style', 'debugging' and performance considerations.	Facilitate general guidelines to ease external development efforts.	Tech Providers

Table 2: Dissemination Material

In the following table, the **dissemination channels** are explained:

DIGITAL CHANNELS			
Measure	Description	Benefits	Stakeholders
Source Code Repository	Make accessible its software repositories through well-known source code management platforms. For this, the project has created a CORTEX ² Group in GitLab.	This measure will encourage other Tech providers to re-use the outcomes easily.	Tech Providers
Open Access to Research	A Zenodo CORTEX² community has been created for this purpose. This will be the online repository to manage and publish material with different access permissions, including peer-reviewed publications, shareable scientific research data, and	Encourage open access publishing platform for scientific articles among the consortium, with no author fees and compliant with open access requirements.	Industrial Ecosystem, Tech Providers, Partnerships, Social Innovators

DIGITAL CHANNELS			
Measure	Description	Benefits	Stakeholders
	another type of resources generated.		
Helpdesk	Email support via a generic contact point (contact@cortex2.eu), including bug tracking and feature requests and a FAQ section on the website. Additionally, the project will dedicate specific channels for technical support to the third-parties, such as the specific email opencall@cortex2.eu	Common problem-solving.	ALL Stakeholders

Table 3: Dissemination Channels

Below is an indicative list of **events** that have been identified as main targets. This list is continuously updated by all project partners while actions per event and per partner are being identified and assigned, depending on the maturity of the project.

EVENTS			
Measure	Description	Benefits	Stakeholders
Webinars / Workshops	CORTEX ² will co-organise 20 webinars and workshops during the project's lifetime as a means of transferring and exchanging technical and socio-economic knowledge with the community, with a total of 500 unique participants.	Workshops will facilitate hands-on training and exchange of ideas, providing opportunities for round table discussions, mentoring and even development.	Industrial Ecosystem, Tech Providers, Partnerships
Conferences / Fairs	Participating in conferences and trade fairs is a strategic mechanism to interact actively with multiple stakeholders.	Showcase results achieved by the project through presentations, talks, exhibition spaces and personal engagement in at least 30 events.	ALL Stakeholders

Table 4: Dissemination Events

The following list introduces some of the **conferences** that the project will emphasise. However, this list is dynamic and gets updated on a frequent basis according to the scientific and technical maturity of the project.

IDENTIFIED CONFERENCES	
Event	Short Description
EuroXR International Conference	The focus of EuroXR conference is on novel VR/AR/MR technologies, including software systems, display technology, interaction devices, and applications. Besides papers on the latest scientific results and highlights from many application fields, the EuroXR conference series aims at creating a unique human-dimension framework, interconnecting European and international XR communities for knowledge cross-fertilisations between researchers, technology providers, and end-users.
Immersive Tech Week	Venue to explore the impact of immersive technologies on our planet, culture, and society. Filled with experiences, talks, round tables, workshops and more for industry leaders, XR enthusiasts, academics, start-ups, scale-ups and policy makers from all over the world.
World Class Connected Industry	Europe's Leading Conference on Industry 5.0, Digital Twins Technology, and Industrial XR.
VR/AR Global Summit	The VR/AR Global Summit, brought by the VR/AR Association, connects the best virtual reality and augmented reality solution providers with enterprise and media entertainment companies.
EU Industry Days	Europe's flagship annual event, highlighting industrial frontrunners and ongoing industrial policy discussions whilst improving the knowledge base of European industry. It is the main platform to discuss industry challenges and co-develop opportunities and policy responses in an inclusive dialogue with a wide range of stakeholders.
Immerse Global Summit Europe	Hosted by the VR/AR Association, focusing on utilising virtual, augmented, and mixed reality (VR/AR/MR) for business growth. The event also covers important industry 4.0 topics such as NFTs, AI, holograms, volumetric capture, edge computing, crypto, and digital real-estate technology.
Web3D	Web3D addresses an extensive range of research, development, and practices related to several 3D application domains including the metaverse, and all topics related to Web/mobile 3D content creation, immersive realities, 3D compression, publishing technology, tools, and related studies.
SME oriented events	

IDENTIFIED CONFERENCES	
Event	Short Description
EU SME Week	A pan-European campaign that aims to promote entrepreneurship in Europe. It helps existing entrepreneurs find information on available support and tries to encourage more people to set up their own businesses. The main event is organised every autumn together with the SME Assembly and the European enterprise promotion awards ceremony.
4YFN	4YFN is the startup event of the world's largest exhibition for the mobile industry, GSMA MWC. Its goal is to support startups, investors and companies to connect and launch new business ventures.
Codemotion	Conference gathering for developers and IT professionals craving for insights on the latest technologies, inspirational talks, and hands-on activities.
EIT Digital Conference	Europe's Flagship Conference on Cybersecurity, Quantum Computing, Metaverse and Green Digital. Showcasing the latest about digital innovation, network with key players from industry, research and academia, and establish new business relations.

Table 5: Identified Events interesting for CORTEX²

3.2. Communication Plan

In the case of CORTEX², **Communication activities involve specific measures for promoting the project itself and the results attained.** The communication plan has the mission to reach out to a broader audience beyond the project's core community.

The plan herein has the mission to reach out to the broadest audience possible. Communication campaigns will be implemented throughout the project lifetime to efficiently build traction among the target audience, emphasising on **CORTEX² innovations and pilots' and third-parties' activities.** Such campaigns will build upon the **Promotion Mix** - the fourth element of the **Marketing Mix**⁴ - that focuses on creating awareness and persuading the audience to initiate the engagement. In the particular case of CORTEX², this Promotion Mix is the integration of **Personal Selling, Digital Marketing, Promotional Material and Branding.**

⁴ <https://neilpatel.com/blog/4-ps-of-marketing/>

Figure 5: The Marketing Mix

Why communicate?

- ✓ Attract the best experts to your team
- ✓ Share best practices with others
- ✓ Promote your project's activities and results
- ✓ Trigger new collaborations & opportunities
- ✓ Generate market demand for the products or services developed
- ✓ Raise citizens' awareness of how their money is spent
- ✓ Show the success of European collaboration
- ✓ It is a legal obligation

Article 17 of the Horizon Europe grant agreement: Obligation to promote the action and its results

Beneficiaries must promote the action and its results by providing targeted information to multiple audiences in a strategic and effective manner (including to the public).

Communicate your project

A comprehensive communication strategy is crucial to promote your project and its results. Your plan should define clear objectives adapted to a range of target audiences. It should be proportionate to the scale of your project.

Go digital:

- Website, videos
- Social media (your account and your institution's)
- Newsletters
- Factsheets

Build networks:

- Events (i.e. conferences, symposia)
- Project & experts meetings
- Reach out to the media

Build your own communication strategy

- 📋 Be strategic: allocate resources, involve professional communicators and ensure continuity.
- 🎯 Set your goals and objectives: make clear what you want to achieve with your communication strategy, and how.
- 👥 Define your audience: include all relevant target groups and tailor your content to each audience. Do you have a media list relevant to your area?
- 🗣️ Choose your message: is it news? Share it with your audience. Keep it simple and remember to tell a story; do not just list the facts.
- 📧 Use a channel that will reach your target audience. Remember to let your Project Officer and [National Contact Point](#) know about your achievements!
- 🏆 Evaluate your efforts: set simple indicators to measure your success.

HORIZON EUROPE

Figure 6: European Commission Communication Principles

3.2.1. Objectives

The main objectives of the communication strategy are as follows:

- Set up internal communication mechanisms among the partners of the consortium.
- Support the external promotion of CORTEX² and its outcomes, managing the branding.

- Deliver top-level messages about the project to all identified and relevant stakeholders.
- Raise awareness to non-specialised audiences of the added value of CORTEX² and its application in pilot activities.
- Increase awareness and interest in the project.

3.2.2. Measures

A series of measures and communication tools will be implemented in order to allow the project to reach the right audiences in a communication friendly and synchronous way.

PERSONAL SELLING			
Measure	Description	Benefit	Stakeholder
Email Campaigns	Implementing targeted email campaigns to stakeholders to raise awareness about the project and its activities. Using EU GDPR-compliant solutions. A portfolio of templates per target will be produced, integrating CTAs.	Broadcasting messages to a target pool of contact points via email is a highly effective measure for promoting activities and results, seeking endorsement for the open calls.	Industrial Ecosystem, Tech Providers, Partnerships
One-to-one Meetings	Follow up action with targeted stakeholders to engage them in future activities and maintain a constant communication flow.	Although this is not a scalable mechanism, one-to-one phone calls and meetings are successful when targeting very specific key actors, often as a follow-up of an email campaign, scouting or event. For the scope of the project, this is especially relevant when engaging policymakers, SMEs managers (open calls) or representatives from Partnerships & Networks.	Industrial Ecosystem, Tech Providers, Partnerships, Policymakers

Table 6: Communication - Personal Channels

DIGITAL CHANNELS			
Measure	Description	Benefit	Stakeholder
Project Website	Establish online presence – a website where the general public	A key instrument for enhancing the visibility of the	ALL Stakeholders

DIGITAL CHANNELS			
Measure	Description	Benefit	Stakeholder
	<p>and interested individuals can read about the project’s progress and findings, including news, results, events, the pilots and Open Calls.</p> <p>See https://cortex2.eu/</p>	<p>project, introducing visitors to CORTEX²'s rationale and educating them about the project concept.</p>	
Open Call Platform	<p>The F6S platform will be used to host and run the open call operations.</p>	<p>The platform counts with a critical mass of 16K members.</p>	Tech Providers
Social Media	<p>CORTEX² will create and maintain actively its presence in a number of social media channels, with particular focus on Twitter and LinkedIn as they have proven to be the most effective tools when engaging with tech communities.</p>	<p>Social media channels are a fast and low-cost way of reaching interest groups and communities that are normally not present at any events or conferences (physical or digital).</p>	ALL Stakeholders
Newsletters	<p>Complementary to email engagement, online newsletters will provide a snapshot of the main activities and achievements of the project. The project will pursue contributing to at least 10 other Newsletters by the EC or associated initiatives. Professional marketing platforms will be used to automate the distribution among all contact points.</p>	<p>The project newsletter shows the progress of the project to all stakeholders and keeps their interest high.</p>	Industrial Ecosystem, Tech Providers, Partnerships
Press Releases	<p>CORTEX² will develop and distribute press releases to mainstream and specialist media as well as relevant civil society newsletters, magazines and journals. Press releases will also be distributed individually by partners to communicate the project to their network of customers, members and collaborators.</p>	<p>Within the communication strategy, press releases can also target specific stakeholders depending on the journal / paper / website where the press release is published or distributed.</p>	Industrial Ecosystem, Tech Providers, Partnerships

DIGITAL CHANNELS			
Measure	Description	Benefit	Stakeholder
	A joint Press Release was launched in M1 to present the project goals and its partners.		
Developer Community	The project will connect and execute promotional activities in open communities and channels of developers, such as Gitter communities , Women Who Code , Women in AI and Hashnode .	Widespread awareness, uptake and validation among the developer community.	Tech Providers
Publishing & Scouting Platforms	CORTEX ² will leverage pre-existing multi-stakeholder portals to promote the project and its open calls, such as EUcalls , CALLforEUROPE or EU Agenda .	Widespread awareness, uptake and validation among the general public.	Tech Providers, Partnerships

Table 7: Communication - Digital Marketing

PROMOTIONAL MATERIAL			
Measure	Description	Benefit	Stakeholder
Printing & Merchandising	This is the predominant element when participating in physical events and meetings, including brochures, flyers, posters, and other laid-out paper-based resources. The material will be available as e-files and printed when needed. CORTEX ² will explore the use of re-usable merchandising as a creative measure that entices the audience to know the project.	Project collateral distributed at various events, conferences, workshops, etc., will gain the project visibility with the general public and the national and European media.	ALL Stakeholders
Slide Decks	Slide decks will replace in some cases the website as 'Point of Market Entry' of the project, mainly in events, email campaigns and one-to-one meetings. CORTEX ² produced the initial slide deck; further versions will be provided to fine-tune content for the target audience and update achievements.	Project presentation to be shared with the broad audience of the project.	Industrial Ecosystem, Tech Providers, Partnerships

PROMOTIONAL MATERIAL			
Measure	Description	Benefit	Stakeholder
Infographics & Banners	Infographics and banners are eye-catching elements to quickly draw attention about the project, its objectives, announcements, partners, or the beneficiaries from the funding instruments. Therefore, the project will design and produce these items regularly, integrating them into the website, social media and newsletters.	Visual content has always proved to be a very effective means of communication.	ALL Stakeholders
Multimedia material	The project will produce at least 3 videos and use clips to have self-explanatory and appealing material for the website and social media, leveraging other available distribution channels of promotion (e.g., YouTube, Vimeo). Public webinars and live training modules will be recorded and made available.	Visual content has always proved to be a very effective means of communication.	ALL Stakeholders
Logo & Templates	CORTEX ² keeps a brand to be used, refined and protected throughout the project. See brand elements in Annex B	Common visual branding.	ALL Stakeholders

Table 8: Communication - Promotional Material

3.3. Dissemination and Communication Monitoring

Monitoring and adjusting the Dissemination and Communication plan on a frequent basis is a fundamental element of the project's success. Continuous monitoring allows the consortium to correct any possible deviations and improve its effectiveness by applying correction and mitigation measures when needed.

It will also address possible implementation problems and identify whether further action is required to ensure that objectives are met. Emphasis is given on the pre-assessment of information needs, the monitoring frequency and the method of collecting evidence.

The execution and effectiveness of the Dissemination and Communication Plan is dependent on a close monitoring, flexible and prompt response mechanism. Every

designed and implemented activity will be monitored and evaluated according to its account and closely related to the KPIs (see **ANNEX A: Dissemination & Communication KPIs**).

Figure 7: Dissemination & Communication Loop

- **Design:** Design is an activity based on the Dissemination & Communication Plan and the desired impact.
- **Execute:** Execute according to plan.
- **Monitor:** Closely monitor the activity and collect input and results. Monitoring will be based on a template that is available only to partners through the internal project's repository (Microsoft Teams CORTEX² group).
- **Evaluate:** Evaluate the outcomes of the activity in a collaborative way according to the desired targets set in the design phase.
- **Learn:** Learn through this evaluation and try to extract the most valuable outcomes out of it.
- **Adjust:** Absorb findings and lessons learnt to adjust the plan accordingly, if needed.

All outcomes and results of the Dissemination and Communication plan will be reported in **D6.2 Impact Interim Report** at Month 18 and **D6.5 Impact Final Report** at Month 36.

3.3.1. Monitoring Strategy

To plan and keep track of all the dissemination and communication activities, the Dissemination and Communication Leader has designed a monitoring tool that all project partners can easily access and use through the Microsoft Teams CORTEX² group.

The monitoring tool, in Excel format, keeps track of every dissemination and communication action (foreseen or done) in the frame of CORTEX² measuring the KPIs achievement and partner's involvement.

D6.1 - CORTEX² Impact Master Plan

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1	CATEGORY	TITLE	DATE	DESCRIPTION	STATUS	LINK	PARTNER(S)	CONTACT POINT(S)
2	Press Release	Extended reality solutions to facilitate remote collaboration	19/09/2022	CORTEX ² kickoff PR	Published	https://rebrand.ly/CORTEX2-LaunchPR-Sept2022	Australo	cortex2@australo.org
3	Blog post	CORTEX ² 's journey to facilitate remote collaboration has begun	8/11/2022	CORTEX ² kickoff announcement	Published	https://cortex2.eu/2022/11/08/cortex2-starts-to-facilitate-remote-collaboration/	Australo	cortex2@australo.org
4	Online reference	2 new Horizon Europe Projects: CORTEX ² and XRECO	14/04/2022	CITIP participation in CORTEX ² announcement	Published	https://www.law.kuleuven.be/citip/en/news/item/archived_news/2-new-horizon-europe-projects-cortex2-and-xreco	KU Leuven	franklyn.ohai@kuleuven.be
5	Online reference	COoperative Real-Time EXperiences with EXTended reality	29/11/2022	CORTEX ² profile at VAM Realities site	Published	https://vam-realities.eu/cooperative-real-time-experiences-with-extended-reality/	External EU-funded project	michael.schwaiger@enter-network.eu
6	Blog post	Start of the CORTEX ² project	-/09/2022	CORTEX ² kickoff announcement	Published	https://av.dfk.de/2022/12/start-of-the-cortex%c2%b2-project/	DKFI	alain.pagani@dfki.de

Figure 8: CORTEX² Monitoring Tool view

3.3.2. Possible Risks

There are a number of risks and potential issues related to the communication and dissemination side of the project. **These risks will be monitored and mitigated** by the Communication & Dissemination leader who will also control these risks on a regular basis and will report any changes to the Project Coordinator. Examples of communication risks include but are not limited to:

DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION RISKS		
Risk	Priority	Measure to minimise the risk
Communication & Dissemination activities fail to target the correct audiences. The project may fail to draw interest from relevant stakeholders and potential Open Call applicants	High	CORTEX ² 's partners have defined a clear set of objectives and measures for each target group. However, this agile strategy allows us to revisit and mitigate our activities if needed. Close monitoring and frequent evaluations will make sure that our strategy will remain on track throughout the project.
Lack of awareness of the novel solution from the user side	Low	Increased dissemination, organisation of launch events. Use of the diverse partners' network which guarantees relevant connections and channels.

Table 9: Dissemination and Communication Risks

3.4. Dissemination and Communication Guidelines

Communication and dissemination efforts are essential to CORTEX² success. Given their importance, all consortium partners must contribute to promoting its objectives, activities, and achievements. The Dissemination and Communication Leader has prepared the following guidelines in order for the CORTEX² consortium to have common rules when it comes to communicate or disseminate project activities and results (see **ANNEX B: Dissemination & Communication Guidelines**).

4. Exploitation and Sustainability

The strategic target of all the exploitation activities will pave the way towards **widespread adoption of CORTEX² results during the project and beyond the end of the project**. In the following sections, we have specified our preliminary exploitation strategy and the required steps aimed at identifying sound business models, replicable to various markets. The main objective of the exploitation activities is to position the CORTEX² project among the identified key stakeholders and maximise its impact during its life through the execution of different activities involving the offline and online world.

4.1. Exploitation principles

CORTEX² recognises **three main** exploitation models for the project results:

- **Commercial exploitation model**, which implies the paid provision of the project results to the end users, complying with a licensing scheme that will be defined at a later stage.
- **Research exploitation model**, which implies the use of the research know-how acquired in future research activities.
- **Technological exploitation model**, which implies the use of the technological know-how gained for the development of innovative products and the provision of advanced services built on top of them.

Figure 9: Exploitation Models

All three routes will be explored independently as the project evolves while the most appropriate exploitation model will be selected. At this point, it is important to highlight that CORTEX² will produce several exploitable results. All exploitable results will be treated on equal terms therefore the most appropriate model for each one will be proposed. However, it also needs to be addressed that the exploitation models of the project's results will be dependent upon three main parameters:

- the nature and interests of the project partners and stakeholders in general,
- the distribution model (commercial or non-commercial) of the project results, and
- the distribution of the IPRs amongst the project partners.

Based on these limitations:

- CORTEX² industrial partners are mainly interested in commercially exploiting the project results,
- the consortium (as well as external) academic and research organisations are mainly interested in adopting the research exploitation model for project results that will be provided as open-source components, integrating them in their research and/or teaching activities and/or setting up future research projects further promoting the project results, and
- external industrial partners are mainly interested in adopting the technological exploitation model for the project results.

4.1.1. CORTEX² added value

The mission of CORTEX² is to bridge the divide between widespread video-conferencing tools and state-of-the art XR-based solutions, **democratising the uptake of next-generation eXtended Reality tele-cooperation** among a number of industrial segments and SMEs. To this aim, our project will provide:

- Full support for AR experience as extension of compatible video-conferencing systems when using heterogeneous services end devices through a novel Mediation Gateway platform
- Resource-efficient teleconferencing tools through innovative transmission methods and automatic summarisation of shared long documents
- User-friendly and powerful XR experiences with instant 3D reconstruction of environments and objects and simplified use of natural gestures in collaborative meetings

During the project, the competitive landscape will be analysed and unique selling points of the CORTEX² results will be highlighted.

4.1.2. Knowledge management and protection strategy

The basic principles concerning intellectual property rights (IPR), background and results, access rights, and rights of use are described in the DoA.

CORTEX² will consider three main elements of an effective system to protect and exploit Intellectual Property (IP):

- Firstly, a system that enables the protection of IP (e.g., patents, copyrights, brand, industrial design) that includes clarity about the ownership and use of IP rights (IPR), the rights and freedom of parties to transfer (assign) IP, and the freedom to publish.
- Secondly, a technology transfer framework, preferably with the support of specialised knowledge transfer offices with professional staff, such as the European IPR Helpdesk.

- Thirdly, a fair law enforcement system in each partner's country caters to dispute settlement and can award penalties and sanctions where appropriate.

Specific IPR issues are identified and addressed in the **Consortium Agreement**. The basic principle is that:

- Foreground knowledge, i.e., created within (or resulting from) the project, belongs to the project partner who generated it.
- If knowledge is developed jointly and separate parts cannot be distinguished, it will be jointly owned unless the concerned contractor agrees on a different solution.
- Background: As per the Grant Agreement (Article 16.1) background is defined as “data, know-how or information (...) that is (...) needed to implement the Action or exploit the results”. Because of this need, Access Rights must be granted in principle, but Parties must identify and agree amongst themselves on the Background for the Project. These specifications are in Attachment 1 of the Consortium Agreement, including:
 - Description of Background
 - Specific restrictions and/or conditions for implementation (Article 16.4 Grant Agreement and its Annex 5, Section “Access rights to results and background”, sub-section “Access rights to background and results for implementing the Action”)
 - Specific restrictions and/or conditions for Exploitation (Article 16.4 Grant Agreement and its Annex 5, Section “Access rights to results and background”, sub-section “Access rights for exploiting the results”)

4.1.2.1 *Joint Ownership of Results*

Joint ownership is governed by Grant Agreement Article 16.4 and its Annex 5, Section Ownership of results, with the following additions:

Two or more beneficiaries own results jointly if:

- they have jointly generated them, and it is not possible to: establish the respective contribution of each beneficiary or separate them for the purpose of applying for, obtaining or maintaining their protection.

The joint owners must agree — in writing — on the allocation and terms of the exercise of their joint ownership (“joint ownership agreement”), to ensure compliance with their obligations under the Grant Agreement.

4.1.2.2 *Transfer of Results*

Each Party may transfer ownership of its own Results, provided this does not affect compliance with their obligations under the Grant Agreement, as stated in Article 16.4 and its Annex 5, Section Transfer and licensing of results, sub-section “Transfer of ownership” of the Grant Agreement.

The beneficiaries must ensure that their obligations under the Agreement regarding their results are passed on to the new owner and that this new owner has the obligation to pass them on in any subsequent transfer.

Moreover, they must inform the other beneficiaries with access rights of the transfer at least 45 days in advance (or less if agreed in writing), unless agreed otherwise in writing for specifically identified third parties, including affiliated entities or unless impossible under the applicable law. This notification must include sufficient information on the new owner to enable the concerned beneficiaries to assess the effects on their access rights. The beneficiaries may object within 30 days of receiving notification (or less if agreed in writing) if they can show that the transfer would adversely affect their access rights. In this case, the transfer may not take place until an agreement has been reached between the beneficiaries concerned.

In case a Party intends to transfer its share of a joint Result, the other joint owner(s) shall have a pre-emptive right to acquire said joint Results.

Each Party may identify specific third parties it intends to transfer the ownership of its Results in Attachment (3) of this Consortium Agreement. The other Parties hereby waive their right to prior notice and their right to object to such a transfer to listed third parties according to the Grant Agreement Article 16.4 and its Annex 5, Section Transfer of licensing of results, sub-section "Transfer of ownership", 3rd paragraph.

The transferring Party shall, however, at the time of the transfer, inform the other Parties of such transfer and shall ensure that the rights of the other Parties under the Consortium Agreement and the Grant Agreement will not be affected by such transfer. Any addition to Attachment (3) after the signature of this Consortium Agreement requires a decision of the Steering Committee.

The Parties recognise that in the framework of a merger or an acquisition of an important part of its assets, it may be impossible under applicable EU and national laws on mergers and acquisitions for a Party to give at least 45 calendar days prior notice for the transfer as foreseen in the Grant Agreement. The obligations above apply only for as long as other Parties still have - or still may request - Access Rights to the Results.

4.2. Exploitation and Sustainability Plan

In CORTEX², exploitation will be tackled in a multidimensional way, aiming to take advantage of all the high-end, innovative outcomes of the project. Different exploitation routes will be examined throughout the project for identifying the most promising exploitation path for each tangible or intangible asset. The figure below provides a graphical overview of the **exploitation path that each exploitable asset** will follow throughout the lifetime of the project.

Figure 10: Exploitation Path

4.2.1. Key Exploitable Assets & Strategy

Key Exploitable Assets (KEAs) are the project's exploitable results, including the knowledge generated and published, the framework of technical features and services released, as well as the strategic relationships created among critical stakeholders.

The consortium has identified the **3 Key Exploitable Assets** that will be of prime interest. Although additional results may be revealed throughout the project's lifetime, independently assessed and tested.

KEA #1: Evolutive Immersive SaaS		
Description	Background IP	Exploitation Strategy
<p>The project will deliver a running infrastructure able to host various instantiated immersive workplaces with predefined immersive environments.</p> <p>This infrastructure will be available in the SaaS model.</p>	<p>This asset will rely on multiple IPs brought by the technical partners: DFKI (XR video processing), LINA (voice processing and meeting minutes generation), ICOM (IoT connectivity platforms and network optimisation knowledge), ALE (Rainbow collaborative platform)</p>	<p>The objective of the consortium is to sell the 3 Cortex² pilots in an "as-a-service" model through the different go-to markets of the consortium participants: direct subscription by end-customers, sold through channel partners, integrated by technology partners in their own solutions, etc...</p> <p>Some services will be provided in an industrialised ready-to-use and easy to subscribe format, making it easy for channels to resell and end customers to adopt.</p> <p>Channel partners and technology partners will be able to customise their own services for end customers by leveraging the openness of the platform to match the expected outcome of their end-customers, both on the device end (SDKs, APIs) and XR modules elements (value-added services defined with their expertise).</p>

KEA #1: Evolutive Immersive SaaS		
Description	Background IP	Exploitation Strategy
		<p>Revenues linked to the different services will be shared with involved partners depending on the XR options involved.</p> <p>Eventually, an “XR services store” could be created to provide visibility to the different services to a wider audience in the various targeted vertical segments.</p>

Table 10: KEA #1: Evolutive Immersive SaaS

KEA #2: CORTEX ² collaborative abstract model		
Description	Background IP	Exploitation Strategy
<p>Publication of a comprehensive and evolutive multimedia abstraction model able to tackle XR and non-XR users as well as complex behaviours involving multiple communication channels (voice, video, etc.) during a given collaboration (R1, R4). Such a framework may be implemented into multiple business cases to produce rich and evolutive immersive environments.</p>	<p>Model designed and developed by technical partners during the project. It will leverage open-source components licensed under compatible license schemas.</p>	<p>This model will be released under an open-source license. Such delivery of open-source components must be accompanied by fostering an open-source community, which can lead to the take-up of components by customers who then buy support, consulting, education, and integration services.</p> <p>Although the release of software under an open-source license does not guarantee broad dissemination and effective exploitation of results by itself, it is a significant enabler. Indeed, this allows third parties, both in academia and in industry, to experiment with the software components, and then get high knowledge and confidence in the CORTEX² results, for possible exploitation, in the mid-to long-term. Moreover, the release of software components under an open-source license enables the results to be enriched by third parties and represents a significant enabler for promoting standards in the mid-to long-term.</p>

Table 11: KEA #2 CORTEX² collaborative abstract model

KEA #3: CORTEX ² Evolutive Technical and Societal Community		
Description	Background IP	Exploitation Strategy
<p>Federation of a growing technical and social community around a core</p>	<p>Leverage F6S, open-source and users</p>	<p>Having a strong technical and societal community is key for the growth of XR usage. Such a community will</p>

KEA #3: CORTEX ² Evolutive Technical and Societal Community		
Description	Background IP	Exploitation Strategy
open and evolutive immersive platform enabling the integration of future evolutions either in the XR technologies or in the XR experiences.	(Actimage, ALE) and developers' communities (Rainbow)	bring a never-ending improvement to the XR capability of the platform while ensuring a human-centred and ethical approach. Hence, the strategy is to foster mutual nurturing between KEA#3 and KEA#2 to grow the community. Openness and abstraction will drive a standardisation approach, ensuring long-term compatibility for multiple and diverse contributors who will populate and enrich the ecosystem. This community will be initiated through the 3 pilots' development and the FSTP instrument. The consortium will pay attention to providing the right support level either from a technical point of view, user point of view, community management point of view or business point of view.

Table 12: KEA #2: CORTEX² collaborative abstract model

4.2.2. Business case

A preliminary Business Case was elaborated at the proposal stage to present the business logic inherent to CORTEX², assessing the market, its driving factors, the unique proposition of the project, the benefits to be created and a preliminary business model to generate revenues and serve customers.

- **Target market**

The European XR market has matured over the course of the last few years. Surrounded by excessive hype in the past, one of the main drivers lies in the increased relevance of XR for enterprise applications, leading to growing investments, especially from big companies, some of which are starting to implement XR into their industrial, business and educational workflows. The COVID-19 pandemic has prompted companies to accelerate their tele cooperation workflows, which should lead to a general familiarisation across the workforce with regard to generic digital skills. In fact, 82% of European XR companies already devote their products and services to digitise training processes, and 46% for conducting meetings⁵. It is estimated that the adoption of XR technologies on employment will become massive, with 1.2 to 2.4 million new jobs directly or indirectly created in Europe by 2025.

In this sense, CORTEX² needs to assess the convergence of two big sectors:

⁵ Ecorys (2020), XR Industry Survey

- the **video conferencing market**, highly influenced by the COVID-19 outbreak (witnessing an increase of 500% in the first two months of the pandemic), exploded by the demand of teleworking and remote social interaction. The European market size is expected to surpass USD 3.7 billion by 2027, growing at over 10% CAGR⁶; and
- the **European XR industry** that is expected to reach between €35-65 billion by 2025, representing a gross added value of between €20-40 billion, and directly create employment for up to 860,000 people⁷.

- **Needs**

There are several factors that influence the uptake of XR solutions by European companies.

- **Economic and time savings:** XR-enhanced remote tele-cooperation would allow for quicker and more accurate maintenance and assembly, reducing the need for experts to travel.
- **Digital skills:** In many EU countries, more than half of the workers who started working from home since the pandemic had no prior experience with teleworking. XR provides meaningful enhancements to physical experiences, with the potential to upskill and augment workers' abilities, productivity and efficiency to errors. Deploying the right capacity-building strategies will lead to creating new jobs and increasingly promoting a multitude of new and cross-disciplinary digital skills to manage effective and productive remote hybrid teams.
- **Funding:** The implementation of a new and often unknown technology comes at a cost, especially for SMEs and startups with limited resources. According to the findings of the Ecorys XR Industry Survey, many EU XR companies (over 26%) operate with self-funds (personal savings/family and friends' support) and over 60% have 10 employees or less. The presence of targeted funds would help companies to make these steps.
- **Sustainability:** Business meetings and collaborative applications in VR/AR can provide users with efficient ways to collaborate remotely, reducing the need to travel and, in turn, reducing CO2 emissions in the transport sector. 71% of EU XR companies report that their solutions help reduce carbon footprint via virtual enhanced meetings.

⁶ 'Europe Video Conferencing Market Forecast to 2027'. Research And Markets, Aug 2020

⁷ 'XR and its potential for Europe'. ECORYS EUROPE, April 2021

- **Unique selling proposition**

CORTEX² will democratise for all types of operators the integration of XR hardware and software into daily industrial processes, enabling next-generation tele-cooperation mechanisms that will accelerate the Future of Work and validating the scalability potential through competitive calls.

- **Benefits**

CORTEX² taps into the benefits of XR-enabled tele-cooperation for conducting traditional tasks in more innovative, faster and more cost-effective ways.

- **Collaborative working:** Possibilities for remote working range from meetings and training to co-design, control and maintenance. Virtual meetings conducted in a 3D environment allow for deeper interaction between attendees, who can share objects such as whiteboards and use them simultaneously.
- **Remote training and supervision:** The use of VR and AR for training enables teachers to share in real-time a virtual environment with students, allowing them to share the manipulations they are doing in the virtual world.
- **Maintenance processes:** The use of VR and AR for maintenance enables understanding phenomena and procedures in industrial processes more quickly and easily. Experts can provide real-time support to personnel on site without the need to travel, saving money and time while reducing their carbon impact. They could also superimpose instructions if personnel are provided with AR headsets or devices, further improving their efficiency.

4.2.3. Exploitation Phases & Next Steps

The actual exploitation plan(s) for any exploitable asset of the project, will be elaborated and updated according to project needs and evolutions taking place throughout the project duration. This will be done during eight different phases:

- **Phase 1:** Market insights and business requirements.
- **Phase 2:** Define project's value proposition.
- **Phase 3:** Business requirements validation.
- **Phase 4:** Business Model.
- **Phase 5:** Identify and explore open issues.
- **Phase 6:** Seek partners' buy in.
- **Phase 7:** Consolidation.
- **Phase 8:** Go-to-market, long-term sustainability and potential commercialisation.

What is important to mention at this point is that the above-mentioned phases are subject to review and refinement during the following months and according to the needs and requirements of the project.

Figure 11: Exploitation Plan Phases

Phase 1: Market insights and business requirements (M12): For the potential commercialisation of a new innovative product, it is essential to have in-depth knowledge of the market and the clients that you want to serve. During CORTEX², different models will be used to get in-depth knowledge of the market:

- **Market insight model:** instructs the team to begin with listing market trends that are specific to their proposition. These market trends help zero down on the target groups the team would want to focus on for their offering. Based on the market trends, the next step is to identify the needs of each of the target groups.
- **Client insight model:** Helps in better understanding the needs of the target groups. The target group is the buyer of the service; however, there are other stakeholders for this buyer, and it is as crucial for the offering to cater not only for the needs of the buyer but also its most important stakeholders.
- **Competition insight model:** Two of the needs identified in the market insight model are plotted on the model. It helps the team determine to what extent the proposition caters to these two needs and hence plot the CORTEX² platform as a solution provider accordingly. When plotted against competitors with offerings in the same space, the model helps identify the whitespaces and translate to differentiation.

The market is explored using standard tools, such as **SWOT**⁸ and **PESTEL**⁹ and so on, to identify and to quantify the market for future forecasting.

Phase 2: Explore the project activities and derive a value proposition (M12): By applying common techniques from the management literature, the activities carried out by the project

⁸ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/SWOT_analysis

⁹ <https://corporatefinanceinstitute.com/resources/management/pestel-analysis/>

will be analysed for the value they create, to whom and by whom. These activities are then organised into a strong statement(s) that represents the flow of value in the project.

Phase 3: Business requirements validation (M12-M18): In the third phase, a survey to test market readiness of the first results of the project with possible future clients will take place. In the survey, all results will be presented to future clients, and they will be asked if in the future they would be interested in such a product, if the product covers their business requirements, if they would like to pay for it and how much, what they see as the strong and weak points of the product, etc. The CORTEX² team will instantiate a build-measure-learn feedback loop. CORTEX² achievements will be continuously validated by potential customers (target group). The survey will consist of questionnaires, focus groups and open discussions.

Phase 4: Business model (M12-M18): Besides market insight, it is also very important to have a good business model to bring the new product(s) successfully to the market. A business model describes the rationale of how an organisation creates, delivers, and captures value. For the development of the business model, we shall rely on the 'Business Model Canvas', from Osterwalder, Pigneur & al¹⁰. This is probably the most popular tool used to design the operations of a new or refocused business. In accordance with the building blocks of the business model canvas, the team will be challenged during this phase of the Fast Track to answer the questions regarding the market, the organisation, and the pricing and business case. Additionally, a chain of sequential and parallel activities of the project will be created. Thanks to the analysis of these activities and having in mind the CORTEX² business model, the CORTEX² consortium will create multiple business scenarios that partners will be willing to follow. The identification of revenue streams and cost centres per scenario is the final step of this phase.

Phase 5: Identify and explore open issues: In the first iteration, the open issues to be identified cover the description, pros, cons, caveats and assumed viability of the scenarios. This translates to the key activities, value, clients and key partner's aspects of the Osterwalder canvas. **This first iteration concludes in M18.** In the second iteration, key resources, relationships and channels are also examined. This completes the business model canvas. **This iteration will last from M24 to M28.**

Phase 6: Seek partner buy-in: In the first iteration of this phase, partners are requested to provide their initial impression of the models and then to explore internally how their individual motivations, activities and existing partnerships can support each model. This complements the viability analysis of step 3 (where the scenario is considered in isolation) by also considering the viability of the partners to deliver the scenario. This step is also part of the individual

¹⁰ Osterwalder, Alexander; Pigneur, Yves; Clark, Tim (2010). Business Model Generation: A Handbook for Visionaries, Game Changers, and Challengers. Strategyzer series. Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons. ISBN 9780470876411. OCLC 648031756

exploitation analysis. **This iterative step lasts from M18 to M20.** In the second iteration, partners must state which resources and investments they can commit to the project and which roles they will accept in the post-project sustainability scenario. This step is synonymous with the joint exploitation plan/joint exploitation commitment of the partners. This step runs **from M28 to M30.**

Phase 7: Consolidation: In both iterations, this step includes consolidating all the work and data collected during the period, including individual exploitation plans, joint exploitation leads, business modelling, market data, stakeholders' feedback and technical results. **This step runs from M20 to M24 and from M30 to M32.** The output of the first iteration will be delivered in the intermediate exploitation report, while the output of the second will be in the final report.

Phase 8: Go to market: The final phase of the Fast Track is the development of a 'Go to Market' plan. This step takes the output of the iterations, covering both the theoretical models proposed, the partner's intentions and commitments and the data through the use cases and stakeholder discussions in order to derive a **full business plan** for the implementation of the solution. The selected business scenario is taken as the baseline for exploitation. The completed business model canvas will complement this value proposition with other aspects of the business model and is then specified using financial projections. IPR agreements and interim results to generate the business plan are also finalised in this plan. This plan is ratified by project partners and any changes to the project and partner roles are implemented to prepare for a transition phase towards the new model. **This step runs from M32 to M36.** This will be described in the final exploitation report.

The intensity of exploitation activities will vary in the project based on the delivery of the project results. In this context, the first preliminary plan and ideas are presented in the present Impact Master Plan.

Then, with the collaboration of the consortium, we will intensify our activities with amore analytical definition of all possible commercial and non-commercial exploitation models and definition and evaluation of the sustainability and viability of possible business models and alternative solutions.

The peak of exploitation activities will be prior to the delivery of the project's results, when the project dissemination activities will also be intense with the purpose of reaching and attracting potential stakeholders and customers.

5. Standardisation

CORTEX² will set out a roadmap for contributing to different standardisation bodies. This activity will identify significant opportunities to push contributions into future standards, pre-normative activities and open collaborative development environments.

5.1. Standardisation Fundamentals

5.1.1. Type of Standards

There are different types of standardisation documents depending on their openness, their development time and their degree of consensus:

Figure 12: Types of standards

A **standard** is a document that specifies requirements for products, services and/or processes. This helps to ensure free movement of goods and encourages exports. Standardisation supports efficiency and quality assurance in industry, technology, science and the public sector. It serves to safeguard people and property and to improve quality in all areas of life.

A **specification** is also a document that specifies requirements for products, services and/or processes. However, in contrast to standards, they do not require full consensus and the involvement of all stakeholders. Specifications are a trusted strategic instrument for quickly and easily establishing and disseminating innovative solutions on the market. A specification is the fastest way for turning research into a marketable product. Drawn up in small working groups, specifications can be published within only a few months. These working groups are excellent for exchanging ideas with other market participants. Any specification can be used as a basis for developing a full standard.¹¹

¹¹ <https://www.din.de/en/about-standards/a-brief-introduction-to-standards>

A **de-facto-standard** is a technical standard that was not developed by a standards committee but rather defined by industrial companies. A de-facto-standard can develop over the years as technically useful and sensible through the practice of many users and various manufacturers.

5.1.2. Levels of Standardisation Work

Standards are developed by different standards bodies at national, European, and international levels, as shown by the example of DIN.

	Germany	Europe	Worldwide
General			
Electrotechnology			
Telecommunications			

Figure 13: DIN as part of the European and international standardisation structure¹²

Therefore, interested parties, like manufacturers, consumers, retailers, universities, research institutes, authorities or testing institutes, send their experts to national standards bodies, like DIN in Germany. These experts are organised in Technical Committees (TCs) and organise and carry out the standardisation work in Working groups (WGs) and Sub committees (SCs).

If the standardisation work takes place on European or international level, the national standards bodies send delegates or experts to work in the committees of the European or international standards bodies as shown hereunder:

¹² <https://www.din.de/en/din-and-our-partners/din-in-europe/european-standardization>

Figure 14: DIN's involvement in European and international standards committees (Delegation principle)

These processes ensure that the voice of each interested party of each participating country will be heard. Formal standards are the product of a consensus-building process of all interested parties to create a valuable basis for all users. This leads to a high acceptance of standards. Standards are voluntary and can be used by anybody. They only become mandatory if they are referred to in contracts, laws or regulations.

European standardisation helps ensure the free flow of goods and the general functioning of the European internal market. The main goal of European standardisation is to unify all standards that apply within Europe.¹³

European Standards are developed by CEN, CENELEC (for electrotechnical standardisation) or ETSI (for telecommunications standardisation) according to the national delegation principle, with each country sending a delegation of experts to represent the national standpoint. This standpoint is developed in national committees that "mirror" the European committees. This way, stakeholders can work together in their own native language - a definite advantage. By taking on the secretariat of a European committee, national members can play a leading role in the committee's work. It is often decisive for national interests to be effectively represented at an early stage of the development of a European Standard. European Standards must be adopted, unchanged, as a national standard, and any conflicting national standards withdrawn.¹⁴

International Standards create a common technical language trade partners can use worldwide, providing a framework for the global market. They open up access to new markets and promote a free - and fair - world trade.¹⁵

¹³ <https://www.din.de/en/din-and-our-partners/din-in-europe/european-standardization>

¹⁴ <https://www.din.de/en/about-standards/din-standards>

¹⁵ <https://www.din.de/en/din-and-our-partners/din-and-international-standardization/international-standardization>

International Standards are developed by ISO, IEC (for electrotechnical standardisation) or ITU (for telecommunications standardisation) according to the national delegation principle, with each country sending a delegation of experts to represent the national standpoint. This standpoint is developed in national committees that "mirror" the international committees. This way, stakeholders can work together in their own native language - a definite advantage. By taking on the secretariat of an international committee, national members can play a leading role in the committee's work. It is often decisive for national interests to be effectively represented at an early stage of the development of an International Standard. The mirror committees also decide whether an International Standard should be adopted as a national standard - this is voluntary, in contrast to the European Standards, which must be adopted nationally.¹⁶

5.2. Standardisation Roadmap

5.2.1. Next steps

- **Committees:** For the comprehensive work on standardisation, it is highly important to have an overview of the standardisation landscape in the field of CORTEX². It is the only way to make sure that the deliverables and results of CORTEX² will address the right stakeholders and that custom-fit standards will be developed by and with the support of the responsible committees. First of all, the relevant standardisation committees will be identified. In the field of CORTEX² there are committees on national, European and international levels.
- **Existing and under development Standards:** In addition to the consideration of the relevant committees, a survey of already existing standards and standards under development in the CORTEX² field is important. Such a list of existing standards and standards under development allows for an assessment in which areas useful standards already exist and thus lays the foundation for subsequent identification of standardisation potentials and needs.

This research will be performed through the identification of relevant keywords as well as known standards already applied by the project partners, and conducted by using the database Perinorm¹⁷.

A dashboard with the full results will be distributed among the consortia.

- **Liaising with Committees and bodies:** European and international Standardisation Organisations propose liaisons to facilitate the collaboration between the standardisation world and the research and innovation community. An analysis of the

¹⁶ <https://www.din.de/en/about-standards/din-standards>

¹⁷ <https://www.perinorm.com/home/default.aspx?ReturnUrl=%2fdefault.aspx>

different liaison processes will be performed, and the connections of the consortium will be leveraged, such as the following:

Main contribution to standardisation by the consortium partners		
Body	Partner	Scope
WebRTC / Janus	ALE	ALE contributes to code and conference of the Janus component. Janus is a core component of the overall solution as it performs the media routing and there may be dependency with the XR behaviours of augmented devices.
AIOTI	ICOM	As a member of AIOTI and Standardisation WG03, ICOM will raise awareness to the role of CORTEX ² in the integration of IoT information in XR applications
ETSI ENI	ICOM	ICOM is a participant of the Experiential Networked Intelligence Industry Specification Group (ENI ISG) and will contribute to intent-based Edge Service Management for resource and energy efficiency considering a Proof of Concept (PoC) for XR services.

Table 13: Main contribution to standardisation by the consortium partner

6. Conclusion

Communication, dissemination and exploitation in Horizon Europe projects are structured to ensure that projects have an impact beyond the mere research outcome. To this end, **CORTEX² has developed the Impact Master Plan, which outlines the most important and critical elements related to its communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy** that must be taken into account throughout the entire project lifetime. The current document is expected to act as a point of reference for current and foreseen communication, dissemination and exploitation activities, while all mentioned activities will be continuously monitored and updated throughout the project's lifetime.

Regarding communication and dissemination, CORTEX² aims to publicise the outcomes of the project, in its different phases, to the right audiences at the right time to demonstrate the ways in which research and innovation are contributing to a European 'Innovation Union'. Communication activities will show our multidisciplinary European consortium achievements in scientific excellence and contribution to competitiveness. In addition, the plan has been made keeping in mind the multidisciplinary nature of CORTEX² members, which allows them to reach very different and well-targeted segments of the identified stakeholders. Some channels have been chosen to accomplish a wider visibility and boost the project through some of the most common means of communication nowadays, such as social networks, events, papers, conferences or email marketing. At the same time, public relations campaigns have been planned to keep all related stakeholders updated on CORTEX²'s progress and results. All these actions must be done under the designed corporate image and by spreading the right messages, so that every communication released to the audience is coherent with the scope of the whole project. To make sure all these procedures are carried out properly, a system of metrics has been designed to measure the obtained results and compare them with the previously set objectives.

Regarding exploitation, the **CORTEX² consortium will continuously monitor and evaluate the project's outcomes**, examine possible exploitation routes and identify the most prominent exploitation pathway for each individual asset. Various possible routes, such as individual and/or joint exploitation, scientific vs commercial exploitation etc., will be examined to define the optimum way to go forward and generate impact beyond the closed borders of the project.

7. ANNEX A: Dissemination & Communication KPIs

DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION KPIs		
Measure	Indicator	Target
Website	No. of Unique Visitors (monthly average)	500
Social media	No. of Followers (total)	3.000
	No. of Impressions (monthly)	100
Publications	Peer-reviewed Scientific Publications in Journals and Conferences	20
	Non-scientific / awareness Publications: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Articles / Blog Posts Newsletters (contribute to 10) Press releases 	50
	Videos edited	3
Events	No. of Events to participate	30
Webinars / Workshops	No. of Webinars / Workshops to (co-)organise: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How-to-apply webinars (2) Internal workshops for third parties (6) 12 public Webinars / Workshops 	20
	No. of Registrations / Participants	300
Open Access	No. of Downloads (total)	1.000
Open Calls campaigns	Successful applications (50 per open call)	100
CORTEX ² ecosystem	Stakeholder network engagement	1.500
	Cooperation with EU projects related to XR technologies	5
	Creation of synergies with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> European Associations Innovation Ecosystems Open-Source communities 	5
		20
		2
Printing / Merchandising	Distribution of Hard-copy items	1.500
Infographics & Banners	Production of graphical elements	100
Multimedia material	Production of videos	3

Table 14: Dissemination and Communication KPIs

8. ANNEX B: Dissemination & Communication Guidelines

Communication and dissemination efforts are essential to CORTEX²'s success. Given their importance, all consortium partners must contribute to promoting its objectives, activities, and achievements. These guidelines will help you with this task.

To share your communication and outreach updates and address any questions or suggestions about them or these guidelines, please contact us at cortex2@australo.org.

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Internal communication

The main internal communication channels of the CORTEX² project, where all information related to dissemination and communication activities will be shared, are:

- **Email**
 - **CORTEX² partners contacts list**, saved in our Teams group (Documents > General > 0.1 Administration > Email Lists) and being continuously updated.
 - **WP6** (Innovation strategy, Dissemination, Exploitation and FSTP) **representatives contact list**, saved in our Communications + Dissemination

Activities Monitoring document in SharePoint (Documents > General > 05-Communication and dissemination) and being continuously updated.

- **Rainbow CORTEX² network**, where we can communicate via chats, audio, or video calls. Access is provided after request to the project coordinator (alain.pagani@dfki.de). Here, we have created the “CORTEX² Communication and Dissemination bubble”, where we can share quick updates, documents and materials related to our WP6 activities.
 - **Microsoft Teams CORTEX² group**: The platform for CORTEX² members to have a shared repository with the project files. The communication and branding materials will be saved in the 05-Communication and dissemination folder. The material that can be shared publicly will also be uploaded to the project’s open-access repository [Zenodo](https://zenodo.org).
 - **Monthly communication calls**: All task leaders from WP6 and, if possible, one representative from each partner organisation should always be present. They will be held from the beginning of 2023 onwards.
- **At least one person from your organisation must be active in these channels and attend our communication calls!**

External communication

Website

CORTEX² website: <https://cortex2.eu/>

Apart from giving a general overview of the project, the website will be continuously updated to share CORTEX²'s progress, activities and achievements, and promote its public consultations and their outcomes, as well as our consortium to external stakeholders.

As a partner, you must contribute to populating the website by sending us your content regularly to cortex2@australo.org.

The content could be about:

- your organisation's participation in project-related scientific publications, events, conferences, awards, etc.,
- the main scientific and technical achievements of the project,
- news related to a given WP/task.

Social media

[Twitter](#): @CORTEX2EU

[LinkedIn](#): @CORTEX2

[YouTube](#): @cortex2

We kindly invite you to follow CORTEX²'s social media accounts — both via your organisation's profiles and the personal profiles of the team members involved in the project. Also, please remember to always mention them in your posts about the project and engage (click, share, comment, react) with our updates!

• Content

In all CORTEX² social channels, we will share content about the solutions we are working on (goals, results, facts, methodology), the partners involved, the project's latest updates, news, and events, as well as interesting external information and resources (articles, events, initiatives, videos, newsletters, reports, eBooks, infographics) relevant to our audience and sector.

- On **Twitter**, we will share more real-time information on events, developments, and external content.
- On **LinkedIn**, we will focus on sharing information about the project and its partners.
- On **YouTube**, we will upload the project's videos, webinars, online events, and interviews.

Your CORTEX² posts could also be about:

- your progress and collaborative work with other partners,
- your participation in meetings, events, and workshops,
- your latest news and publications,
- interesting external resources related to the topic of the project.

• Tone

We recommend that you talk about the project in a clear, concise, informal, engaging, and positive way;

- use simple and approachable language,
- make creative and innovative content,
- and don't be afraid to use humour and be entertaining!

• Hashtags to use in your posts

- **#CORTEX2**: When talking about the project on channels where it doesn't have an account and can't be mentioned (out of Twitter, LinkedIn, and YouTube).

- **#CORTEX2news:** When sharing news about the project.
- **#CORTEX2Team:** When talking about the organisations and people involved with the project.
- **#CORTEX2LearningPill:** When talking about the project’s key concepts.
- Related to the project’s sector and subject:
 - #ExtendedReality #VirtualReality #AugmentedReality #MixedReality #XR #VR #AR #MR #ImmersiveTechnologies #Metaverse #IoT #3D #AI
 - #RemoteCollaboration #RemoteTeamCollaboration #RemoteCooperation #TeleCooperation #RemoteSupport #VideoConferencing #NewWaysOfWorking #FutureOfWork #RemoteWork #RemoteTraining #BusinessMeeting #OnlineMeeting
 - #DigitalTransition #DigitalTransformation #DigitalTechnology #Technology #Digitalization #Innovation #Research #Science #Inclusion #Efficiency #Sustainability #OpenSource
 - #TechStartups #SMEs #FSTP
 - #EUfunded #HorizonEU
- Recommended number of hashtags to use per channel:
 - Twitter: 1-2
 - LinkedIn: 1-5
 - YouTube: 3-5
 - Instagram: 3-5
 - Facebook: 2-3

Partners and EU organisations social media profiles

Social media profiles to communicate with or mention in our posts about CORTEX² so that they have a wider reach.

• Partners

Twitter	LinkedIn
@DFKI	Deutsches Forschungszentrum für Künstliche Intelligenz (DFKI)
@AustraloTeam	AUSTRALO
@linagora , @LinagoraLabs , @jplorre	LINAGORA , Jean-Pierre LORRE

Twitter	LinkedIn
@ALUEnterprise	Alcatel-Lucent Enterprise
@IntracomTelecom	Intracom Telecom, Vasileios Theodorou, PhD
@f6s , @F6S_Gov	F6S, F6S Innovation
@KU_Leuven , @CiTiP_KULeuven	KU Leuven, Centre for IT & IP Law (CiTiP) @KU Leuven
@ActimageGmbH	Actimage
@UJuniversitat , @Labpsitec	Universitat Jaume I, Labpsitec Valencia
@CEA_Officiel , @CEA_List	CEA, CEA-List

- **EU organisations**

Twitter	LinkedIn
@EU_Commission	European Commission
@HorizonEU	—
@EUScienceInnov	EU Science, Research and Innovation
@EU_HaDEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA)
@REA_research	European Research Executive Agency (REA)
@DigitalEU	EU Digital & Tech
@EUeic , @EU_EISMEA	European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA)
@XtendRealityEU	—

→ Do you know of other social media profiles that could be useful for the project? Send them to cortex2@australo.org, and we will include them in this document.

- To search for partners' profiles in other channels, have a look at their websites:

- [DFKI](#)
- [AUSTRALO](#)
- [LINAGORA](#)
- [Alcatel-Lucent Enterprise](#)
- [Intracom Telecom](#)
- [F6S](#)
- [KU Leuven, Centre for IT & IP Law \(CiTiP\)](#)
- [Actimage](#)
- [Universitat Jaume I](#)
- [CEA, CEA-List](#)

Newsletters

If your organisation is going to include information about CORTEX² in a newsletter, please tell us about it at cortex2@australo.org at least two weeks in advance so that we can share the information and materials you may need.

- Once the newsletter has been sent, you can report it in SharePoint in the project's Communications + Dissemination Activities Monitoring document, so that we can have a record of the newsletters in which it has appeared.
- Also, add all other online references your organisation makes about the project in this document (in your organization's website, the press, journals, blogs, etc.).

PR material

CORTEX² PR material will be available in SharePoint in the project's communication and dissemination folder. Our press releases will also be posted on the project website and [Zenodo](#).

PR material will be available online and printed whenever necessary (e.g., for events, conventions, workshops) — by Australo or other project partners, depending on volume and logistics.

This material, whether in electronic or hard copy format, must always include:

- CORTEX² social media ([Twitter](#) + [LinkedIn](#)) and [website](#) links.
- CORTEX² and the [EU flag](#) logos.
- EU-funded claim: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101070192.

Merchandising

For any merchandising material your organisation may need to print or produce, please request a free quote from several suppliers (at least three) before placing your order. In any case, please [contact us](#) beforehand to assist with designs and other related tasks.

Participation in events

If your organisation is going to participate in an event, conference, webinar, workshop or meeting that can impact CORTEX², please let us know at cortex2@australo.org within at least two weeks' notice so that we can prepare a communication campaign and promote it on the project's channels. We can also inform the rest of the consortium members so they can promote it among their community and participate.

Steps to take when participating in events

1. BEFORE the event

- Inform [CORTEX²'s communication team](#) at least two weeks in advance.
- Mention CORTEX² and tag its accounts when promoting the event on social media.
- Use the CORTEX²'s PPT template (available in SharePoint) if you are representing the project. You can use your company's template if you are just mentioning it in your presentation. Still, you must
 - indicate you are part of CORTEX²,
 - add CORTEX² and the [EU flag](#) logos with the acknowledgement: CORTEX² has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101070192.

2. DURING the event

- Publish content about it on social media, mentioning CORTEX² and tagging its accounts.
- You can also share content (text + graphic material) with [us](#), so we can publish it on CORTEX² accounts during and after the event.

3. AFTER the event

- Report your participation in the project's Communications + Dissemination Activities Monitoring document in SharePoint, in the **Events tab**.
- Create a blog post about your participation in the event — with the main highlights and takeaways, interesting stories, and data.
- Send the blog post to cortex2@australo.org so we can publish it on CORTEX² website and social media.
- Share pictures and materials from the event with us. Share materials in our SharePoint Events participation folder (there, create a folder with the event's name) and [let us know by email](#) so we can share them in our channels.

Technical & scientific publications

- Please send your organisation's technical & scientific publications about CORTEX² (conference papers, journal papers, etc.) to cortex2@australo.org two weeks before publishing them so that we can review them.

Once they're published, include them in the project's Communications + Dissemination Activities Monitoring document in SharePoint, in the **Scientific Publications tab**.

We welcome all partners to identify and propose opportunities to publish technical outcomes (articles, workshops, congresses).

Open access repository

The CORTEX² open access repository is available at [Zenodo](#).

Please, send the scientific publications, papers, articles, press releases and other public materials you create in the project context to cortex2@australo.org so we can publish them on [Zenodo](#)¹⁸, the open-access repository for the project, where a [CORTEX² community](#) has been created:

The European Commission launched [Open Research Europe \(ORE\)](#), an open-access platform for research from Horizon 2020, Horizon Europe and Euratom funding across all subject areas.

ORE upholds the principles of open science by publishing articles immediately, followed by transparent and open peer review, including supporting data and materials. Reviewers' names are public, as are their reviews, which are also citable. Article-level metrics continuously track the scientific and societal impact of publications. In short, ORE gives everyone, researchers and citizens alike, free access to the latest scientific discoveries.

Publishing in ORE is optional. The European Commission covers all costs upfront, so there is no author's fee or administrative burden. In addition, automatic compliance with Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe open access requirements is guaranteed. Lastly, ORE is also a solution to publish articles even after the Horizon Europe grant has ended.

¹⁸ <https://about.zenodo.org/>

● Project materials and brand identity elements

Some of the materials presented below will be modified and enriched according to the project's needs.

The project in a nutshell

You can use this CORTEX² description in different contexts, such as emails, presentations, social media, websites, etc.

The COVID-19 pandemic pushed individuals and companies worldwide to work primarily from home or change their work model to stay in business. Today, all the signs are that remote work is here to stay. But not all organizations are ready to adapt to this new reality, where team collaboration is vital.

Existing services and applications aimed at facilitating remote team collaboration — from video conferencing systems to project management platforms — are not yet ready to support all types of activities efficiently and effectively. And extended reality (XR)-based tools, which can enhance remote collaboration and communication, present significant challenges for most businesses.

The mission of CORTEX² is to democratize access to the remote collaboration offered by next-generation XR experiences across a wide range of industries and SMEs.

To this aim, CORTEX² will provide the following:

- Full support for **augmented reality (AR) experiences** as an extension of video conferencing systems when using heterogeneous service end devices through a novel Mediation Gateway platform.
- Resource-efficient **teleconferencing tools** through innovative transmission methods and automatic summarization of shared long documents.
- Easy-to-use and powerful **XR experiences** with instant 3D reconstruction of environments and objects, and simplified use of natural gestures in collaborative meetings.
- Fusion of vision and audio for **multichannel semantic interpretation** and enhanced tools such as **virtual conversational agents** and **automatic meeting summarization**.
- Full **integration of internet of things (IoT) devices into XR experiences** to optimize interaction with running systems and processes.
- **Optimal extension possibilities and broad adoption** by delivering the core system with **open APIs** and launching **open calls** to enable further technical extensions, more comprehensive use cases, and deeper evaluation and assessment.

Overall, **we will invest a total of 4 million Euros in two open calls**, which will be aimed at

1. recruiting tech start-ups/SMEs to co-develop CORTEX²
2. engaging new use cases from different domains to demonstrate CORTEX² replication through specific integration paths
3. assessing and validating the social impact associated with XR technology adoption in internal and external use cases

The CORTEX² consortium is formed by 10 organizations in 7 countries, which will work together for 36 months.

CORTEX² has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101070192.

For more information, visit <https://cortex2.eu/>

Brand elements

CORTEX² brand elements include the name, logo, fonts, and colours that the consortium must use in all communication and dissemination activities about the project. A “Branding Elements” document has been shared with all partners throughout SharePoint (General > 05-Communication and Dissemination > 01. Communication & Branding Guidelines).

Project name: CORTEX² (in documents) / **CORTEX2** (online)

The name of the project must be written in capital letters.

Logo

Partners can download it from the Official CORTEX² logo folder in SharePoint and [Zenodo](#).

Versions: Main - Alternate - Black/White.

- It is unalterable, so it is strictly forbidden to modify it in any way.
- It must be visible in its entirety and placed on a background that does not compromise its integrity.
- It must always be surrounded by a free space or a protected area where no other element (text, image, drawing, figure, etc.) can infringe on it.
- When adding the logo to your company's website or any other online platform, please link it to the [project website](#). Ideally, it should appear before any user interaction options (click,

scroll, comments section, etc.), and it does not need to appear on pop-up windows or redirected pages.

There are a few things to consider when using its different versions.

- Whenever possible, the main logo should always be preferred.
- If the background on which it is to be placed has a medium colour or the gradient of the brand (purple to green), the white logo should be preferred.
- The black logo should only be used when colour is unavailable (i.e., black & white printing, embossing on specific materials, laser etching, etc.).

Fonts

- Titles: **Archivo Bold** - [download](#).
- Longer texts: **Open Sans** - [download](#).

Colors

- Primary
- Dark purple: #6E5EBB
- Green: #00F7CE

primary

- Secondary
- Blue: #005066
- Magenta: #B100AF
- Pink: #FF88A2
- Light green: #BEFCE2

secondary

- Neutrals
- White: #FFFFFF
- Grey: #666666

neutrals

PPT and Word templates

PPT and Word templates with all CORTEX² brand elements included can be found in the Project SharePoint Templates folder.

You can use these templates to promote CORTEX² in meetings and events. Remember to export their PDF version when presenting!

Imagery

To avoid copyright issues with the images you use in your project communications, it is best to use Creative Commons licensed images, or free-for-commercial use/no attribution required images that can be found in online image libraries.

1. Creative Commons licenses are a set of copyright licenses that offer the creator of a work a simple way to give the public permission to share and use their work under their terms and conditions.

These licenses are composed of four features:

- Attribution (BY) requires referencing the original author.
- Share Alike (SA) allows derivative works to be made under the same or a similar license.
- Non-Commercial (NC) obliges that the work is not used for commercial purposes.
- No Derivative Works (ND) does not allow the work to be modified in any way.

Free images for commercial use that you can use without risking legal problems are

- Images whose author has given you written permission.
 - Images that have a Creative Commons 0 or CC0 License. The CC0 License indicates that they are public domain images, and you can use them freely for commercial use, modifying them without the need to refer to their author.
2. When using image libraries, make sure that their images indicate that they are free for commercial use or no attribution is required, like in this example:

3. You can find suitable images for the communication of the project in online free image libraries, such as:

- [Google images](#)

Google is a good place to start searching for images since results will include photos from Flickr and other stock photography sites.

In the advanced image search, enter keywords and specify the size, aspect ratio and other details about the image you need. At the end of the form, select the usage rights that apply. Once you've found an image you like, click through to the page to double-check its license.

- [The Stocks](#)
- [Unsplash](#)
- [Gratisography](#)
- [Death to the Stock Photo](#)
- [Reshot](#)
- [ISO Republic](#)
- [FOCA Stock](#)
- [Pixabay](#)
- [Canva](#)
- [ShotStash](#)
- [FreePhotos](#)
- [Picjumbo](#)
- [Pexels](#)
- [Barnimages](#)

GDPR compliance

GDPR compliance is crucial for many of the activities within the project (newsletters, webinars, bootcamps, interviews, etc.).

The EU GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) applies to everybody who handles the personal data of European citizens. The legislation gives individuals rights over what organisations do with their data and includes strict fines for organisations that fail to comply.

Newsletters

1. Data permission

Data permission is about how we manage email opt-ins (people who subscribe to our newsletters). We cannot assume that they want to be contacted according to the GDPR. Leads, customers and partners need to confirm that they want to be contacted explicitly. Therefore, a pre-ticked box automatically opts them in, and people must confirm they want to be contacted deliberately.

CORTEX²

Newsletter Subscription

Subscribe to our newsletter and stay updated.

Enter your email address to subscribe*

Provide your email address to subscribe. For e.g abc@xyz.com

Enter your FIRSTNAME*

Customize this optional help text before publishing your form.

I agree to receive your newsletters and accept the data privacy statement.

You may unsubscribe at any time using the link in our newsletter.

 We use Sendinblue as our marketing platform. By Clicking below to submit this form, you acknowledge that the information you provided will be transferred to Sendinblue for processing in accordance with their [terms of use](#)

SUBSCRIBE

2. Data access

Our subscribers must be able to access their data. Also, the right to be forgotten allows them to have obsolete or inaccurate personal data deleted.

For us, it can be as simple as including an unsubscribe link in our newsletters and mailings and linking it to where users can manage their email preferences.

Example:

3. Data focus

Try to avoid collecting any unnecessary data and stick with the basics.

GDPR-compliant online events

Key GDPR-related aspects to consider when creating an event registration form:

- Don't collect more information than you need to. For example, information about the gender of participants is sensitive and does not always need to be collected. One option could be to make responding to these types of fields optional.
- When indicating how participants can exercise their rights, include an email address in use and monitored regularly.
- Be transparent about why you are collecting data and with whom you will share it.

Public consultations

Public consultations often collect personal data to use in a consultation. Therefore, the collection and further processing of such data will fall within the scope of the GDPR.

Even if the data is simply collected and stored, with no active steps taken to "use" it, the conditions set by the GDPR will still apply. For example, you must ensure adequate data security or that no more data is retained than necessary.

EU logo, acknowledgement & disclaimer

EU logo and acknowledgement

As recipients of EU funding, we have to use the [European flag](#) and emblem in our communication to acknowledge the support received under EU programs.

You can adapt this acknowledgement text depending on what you need to deliver or submit.

EU disclaimer

It is also necessary to include a disclaimer in any document you have to deliver within the scope of the project — a statement that denies liability and is intended to prevent civil liability arising from certain acts or omissions.

The content of this document does not represent the opinion of the European Union, and the European Union is not responsible for any use that might be made of such content.
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Text can appear on the right, left, bottom or top, depending on your needs, and in various fonts.

For more information, please follow the [guidelines on using the EU emblem](#) in the context of EU funding and apply the indicated [graphic rules](#).

9. ANNEX C: Website and Social Media Channels

Website

Within the activities of Dissemination and Communication of the project, the CORTEX² website has been designed and implemented at <https://cortex2.eu/>, with the following structure:

- **Home (<https://cortex2.eu/>)** — Describing the tagline, main purpose, values of CORTEX², consortium, value proposal for the participants of the Open Calls, along with a call to action to subscribe to the Newsletter and the EU funding/privacy policy and Terms of Use disclaimers.

We will select 30 projects through two rounds of open calls — 20 to co-develop specific modules of our platform and 10 new uses-cases with associated tech-developments.

In total, we will invest €4 million in Financial Support to Third Parties (FSTP).

WHAT'S IN IT FOR YOU?

CO-DEVELOPMENT	USE-CASE
€ 2,000,000 TOTAL BUDGET	€ 2,000,000 TOTAL BUDGET
20 PROJECTS	10 PROJECTS
UP TO € 100,000 BUDGET PER PROJECT	UP TO € 200,000 BUDGET PER PROJECT
9 MONTHS DURATION	UP TO 15 MONTHS DURATION

- Capacity building on CORTEX2 and XR technologies & trends
- Access to tech and business experts
- Access to infrastructure and toolkit to facilitate understanding and integration

STAY TUNED!

Subscribe to our newsletter and follow us on social media. To be the first to know about our upcoming calls and keep up to date with everything related to CORTEX2.

OUR CONSORTIUM PARTNERS

10 PARTNERS

7 COUNTRIES

36 MONTHS

UNIVERSITAT JAUME I, DFK, LINAGORA, a, cea, AUSTRALO, FGS, INTRACOM RESEARCH, Alcatel-Lucent Enterprise, KU LEUVEN

From academia and research organisations to technical Information and Communications Technology (ICT) providers and SMEs, our team brings expertise in VR, AR, AI, VR, AI, video conferencing tools, psychology and ethics to build next-generation XR tele-cooperation solutions.

SUBSCRIBE TO OUR NEWSLETTER

SUBSCRIBE

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreements N° 101070192.

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Specific sections have been dedicated to:

- **Project** (<https://cortex2.eu/project/>) — explaining the main technologies tackled, along with the challenges encountered and the approach that the project will use to reach its goals:

What is extended reality (XR)?

XR is used as an umbrella term to describe the immersive technologies that can connect physical and virtual worlds. From the technologies that already exist — augmented reality (AR), virtual reality (VR), and mixed reality (MR) —, to those that are still to be created.

VIRTUAL REALITY

AUGMENTED REALITY

MIXED REALITY

EXTENDED REALITY

OUR APPROACH

To ensure large adoption and fast scaling of our XR remote cooperation solution, we will develop an innovative digital workplace using the teleconferencing solution *Rainbow*, from our partner Alcatel Lucent Enterprise, as a backbone.

Our XR framework will be open, versatile, inclusive, scalable and privacy aware.

- **Pilots** (<https://cortex2.eu/pilots/>) — describing the 3 pilots to be implemented:

- **Team** (<https://cortex2.eu/team/>) — where the members of the consortium are identified.
- **Open Calls** (<https://cortex2.eu/open-calls/>) — specific section dedicated to explaining the main aspects of the open call, such as eligible applicants, type of calls, as well as funding and support offer.

2
OPEN CALLS

30
IDEAS

€4
MILLION

WE ARE LOOKING FOR 30 XR INNOVATORS

Once we have developed the backbone and specific features of the CORTEX2 XR platform, we will look for partners to provide new modules to improve its functionalities, adaptability and replicability in new domains and use cases.

From **research-oriented institutions** (technical universities, RTOs, spin-offs) to **business-driven organisations** (highly risk-taking startups, innovation units in large-scale industry). We will also highly consider technical committees driving standardisation and **open source** efforts.

- **News** (<https://cortex2.eu/news/>) — where the main updates, interviews and articles of the project are being published.
- **Contact** (<https://cortex2.eu/contact/>) — to contact our team to ask questions, explore possible synergies, invite us to events, workshops or conferences, as well as to send us any media and public relations enquiries.

Calls to action to follow the project in Social Media as well as subscribe to the project’s newsletter are used throughout the site.

Social Media

CORTEX² has created and maintains actively its presence in a number of social media channels, with particular focus on:

[LinkedIn:](#)

[Twitter:](#)

